

DEEP LEARNING-BASED EARLY PARKINSON'S DISEASE DETECTION FROM BRAIN MRI IMAGE

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Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD), which significantly impacts the quality of life for millions of older adults worldwide, has emerged as a serious condition affecting the brain and spinal cord. Effective treatment and management of PD rely on early detection and accurate diagnosis. However, diagnosing PD has been challenging due to its similarities with other neurological disorders, leading to a 25% rate of incorrect manual diagnoses.

Brain MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) has shown considerable potential in detecting and diagnosing Parkinson's disease. This study proposes using convolutional neural networks (CNNs), a type of deep neural network architecture, to classify Parkinson's disease and differentiate between PD patients and healthy controls. The study utilizes the Parkinson Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) dataset for classification.

The Parkinson's disease recognition system leverages CNN to analyze the images. The performance of the proposed approach is evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and Area under the Curve (AUC)

Keywords: MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), AUC (Area Under Curve).

1. INTRODUCTION

Several methods are currently used in clinical settings as part of a computer-aided diagnostic approach to analyze patient data. Parkinson's disease (PD) is a degenerative neurological disorder that affects the brain's motor center and cannot be completely cured. Early diagnosis can provide temporary relief to patients and potentially slow the progression of the disease. PD results from the degeneration of dopamine neurons in the substantia nigra, a part of the midbrain rich in dopamine neurons. These neurons release dopamine to communicate with other neurons in specific parts of the nervous system. When dopamine neurons in the substantia nigra start to deteriorate, Parkinson's disease (PD) develops. As a result, patients experience symptoms such as stiffness, slowness of movement (bradykinesia), and resting tremors. Additional symptoms include fatigue, anxiety, depression, slowed thinking, and voice issues. PD is the second most common neurological disorder in elderly individuals, following Alzheimer's disease. While the exact cause of PD remains unclear, it is believed to involve a combination of genetic and environmental factors.

Due to a shortage of specialized medical facilities, most diagnoses occur at an advanced stage of the disease. Experts typically rely on patient history and neurological examinations to make a diagnosis.

However, this approach is less reliable because other neurodegenerative disorders present with similar symptoms. Often, PD is only identified when the levels of dopamine are significantly depleted. It is estimated that approximately 25% of diagnoses are incorrect. Accurate diagnosis of PD remains challenging, and patients who are misdiagnosed as healthy may experience disease progression that becomes more difficult to manage over time.

Several clinical tests can aid in diagnosing PD, but visual imaging techniques offer a suitable approach because they relate directly to the brain's biological features. Two imaging methods commonly used for PD diagnosis are Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT).

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurological disorder that affects approximately 6 million people worldwide. The symptoms of PD progressively worsen over time, leading to a significant decline in quality of life (QOL) and a notable reduction in life expectancy. Although there is currently no cure for PD, various pharmacological and surgical treatments are effective in managing the disease's impact on patients' lives. Achieving an early and accurate diagnosis is essential for improving a patient's QOL by enabling access to appropriate treatments.

Currently, physicians typically diagnose PD based on subjective clinical evaluations of the patient's symptoms. However, research shows that around 25% of PD diagnoses are inaccurate when compared to the results of post-mortem autopsies. Diagnosing PD is complicated due to the presence of other neurological disorders that mimic PD and the variability in symptom severity over time.

Various methodologies are used to identify Parkinson's disease (PD), and the application of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms has shown promising results in recent studies. In the field of image analysis, significant progress has been made in automated medical image segmentation, as manually labeling large volumes of medical images is both time-consuming and prone to errors. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have enabled high performance in automated medical image analysis, achieving results comparable to those of radiologists in tasks such as cardiac MRI segmentation and malignant lung nodule detection.

2. RELATED WORKS

The Olanrewaju et al. study focused on developing a multi-layered feed-forward neural network to identify Parkinson's disease using a machine learning-based technique [4]. They utilized a dataset from the Oxford datasets on Parkinson's illness, which included voice recordings from 23 patients and 31 other participants. The researchers measured 8 frequency-based characteristics related to tremors and employed 10 hidden neurons and 8 input nodes in their neural network. They used the k-means technique for data classification.

Common symptoms of Parkinson's disease, such as loss of smell, constipation, and sleep disturbances, often appear years before motor symptoms develop. As the disease progresses, additional symptoms like tremors, balance issues, and voice impairments become evident. Early-stage treatment is crucial to slowing the progression of the disease or preventing its development. However, diagnosing PD based solely on clinical symptoms remains challenging and complex.

Since 90% of people with Parkinson's disease experience voice disorders, using voice data has become one of the most significant approaches for PD detection. In this method, analyzing acoustic signals

plays a key role in early diagnosis . In the early stages, voice abnormalities are often too subtle to be detected by listeners but can be identified through detailed analysis of voice cues.

Parkinson's disease and other movement disorders are typically categorized into two phases: the preclinical phase, where neurodegeneration occurs without visible clinical symptoms, and the prodromal phase, where clinical symptoms are present but not yet sufficient for a definitive diagnosis. The simulation results indicated that the proposed method achieved accuracy levels of up to 80%, with a specificity of 63.6% and a sensitivity of 83.3%. However, it's important to note that the study did not use actual data to validate this procedure.

Parkinson's disease is a neurodegenerative condition that affects a person's movement due to a lack of dopamine production in the brain. Early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease is crucial for timely treatment and management of the condition. However, the current diagnostic process involves multiple tests and specialist examinations, which can be time-consuming and costly. This study proposes a novel approach to early diagnosis by analyzing voice disorders associated with Parkinson's disease. The researchers extract a set of features from recordings of a person's voice and apply machine-learning methods to analyze and distinguish between Parkinson's cases and healthy individuals.

Hui et al. [22] proposed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to analyze the EEG recordings of 16 healthy individuals and 15 patients with Parkinson's disease. The EEG signals were converted into spectral diagrams using a Gabor transform to train the CNN. Similarly, Majid et al. [23] developed a method based on spatial patterns for diagnosing PD in patients both on and off medication. The EEG signals were preprocessed to remove noise using a common spatial pattern technique. Key features were then extracted from the optimized signals and input into machine learning classifiers, achieving notable performance in distinguishing between patient groups.

In the study by Prashanth et al. [6], the researchers focused on the activator stage, which is characterized by loss of smell in the nasal cavity and sleep disorders. They used sleep pattern data from the PPMI dataset along with 40 features from the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT). To identify PD, they employed Support Vector Machine (SVM) and a classifier, both achieving an accuracy rate of 84.26%. Additionally, only a subset of dopaminergic imaging features was used, limiting the overall efficiency and scope of the analysis.

In a study by Ghanad and Ahmadi [7], the authors proposed a new model for Parkinson's disease identification. They used Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to extract the optimal features from the data and Naive Bayes for classification. The dataset used for this research was obtained from the UCI data archive and consisted of 23 attributes and 197 samples. The model achieved an accuracy rate of 97.5% in the simulation. However, the performance of this model declined significantly when applied to larger datasets.

Luigi et al. [24] extracted frequency features from velocity and angle signals, selected relevant features, and optimized machine learning classifiers for detecting freezing of gait (FOG) before its onset. The FOG detection network achieved strong results and was validated on patient data, with a sensitivity of 84.1%, a specificity of 85.9%, and an accuracy of 86.1%. This indicates that the network can effectively predict FOG before it occurs.

Similarly, Nalini et al. [25] used three deep learning models—Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)—to analyze the voice

characteristics of PD patients. They evaluated the models using loss-function curves for PD detection, with the LSTM network demonstrating superior performance compared to the other models.

Arti et al. [26] employed three machine learning (ML) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) algorithms to diagnose a speech dataset. Data collection and feature selection were enhanced using a combination of wrapper and filtering methods. Support Vector Machine (SVM) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) achieved an accuracy of 87.17%, while Naive Bayes obtained an accuracy of 74.11%.

Similarly, Hajer et al. [27] used three ML algorithms to analyze a PD dataset for distinguishing Parkinson's patients from healthy controls. The data were processed using Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). K-means and DBSCAN models were developed based on these feature-reduction techniques. LDA outperformed PCA, and its outputs were used as inputs for clustering algorithms. DBSCAN achieved an accuracy of 64%, a sensitivity of 78.13%, and a specificity of 38.89%.

Additionally, Moumita et al. [28] designed three models using decision-forest and SysFor algorithms with ForestPA features for PD diagnosis. This approach required a minimal number of decision trees to achieve high accuracy. Increasing the density of decision trees for dynamic training and testing of new samples proved to be the most effective method for detecting PD.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

Deep Learning with CNN for Disease Prediction: A Case Study on Parkinson's Disease using MRI Data [1], Parkinson's Disease (PD) is one of the more prevalent neurodegenerative disorders, with its progression classified into several stages: prodromal, stage 1, stage 2, stage 3, and severe conditions. Due to various limitations in clinical settings, accurately identifying the stage of PD and predicting its progression can be challenging. This highlights a growing need to leverage both supervised and unsupervised artificial intelligence and machine learning methods on clinical and paraclinical datasets to improve diagnosis, stage identification, and progression prediction of PD.

In contemporary neuro-medicine, MRI data is considered valuable for detecting various brain pathologies. Furthermore, recent advancements have shown an increasing use of deep learning techniques in image processing, often yielding impressive results. In this study, we applied Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to develop a model aimed at distinguishing the different stages of PD effectively.

IoT Based Real-Time Remote Patient Monitoring System [2], Parkinson's Disease (PD) is among the most prevalent neurodegenerative disorders, primarily caused by the loss of dopamine-producing neurons. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) can capture structural changes in the brain associated with dopamine deficiency in PD patients. Early diagnosis using computer-aided systems is a critical area of research, as it offers potential for more accurate and timely detection.

Deep learning models can significantly assist clinicians in diagnosing PD and provide objective patient classification. This study uses a deep learning approach to distinguish between PD and healthy control subjects, a process that can be complex and time-consuming when performed manually. Research suggests that the chances of effective treatment increase significantly with early intervention, and valuable time can be saved if the detection process is automated.

In this paper, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based on the LeNet-5 architecture was utilized to classify MRI data of PD patients versus healthy controls successfully.

Magnetic resonance imaging image analysis of the therapeutic effect and neuroprotective effect of deep brain stimulation in Parkinson's disease based on a deep learning algorithm [3], To investigate the therapeutic neuroprotective effects of Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) in Parkinson's Disease (PD), this study employs a deep learning algorithm in combination with Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) analysis. The focus is on evaluating the clinical efficacy of DBS as a surgical treatment for PD, as well as its neuroprotective benefits and impact on neurological recovery post-surgery.

A deep learning model based on MRI image analysis was developed to compare motor function assessments using the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) and improvements in daily living abilities before and after DBS surgery. The model's accuracy and detection speed were also evaluated. The constructed models demonstrated an accuracy rate exceeding 90% for PD detection, with detection speeds ranging from 60 to 200 milliseconds under large-scale data conditions.

The results indicate that DBS significantly improves various clinical symptoms in PD patients. The deep learning model utilizing MRI image analysis proved effective, confirming that DBS not only alleviates symptoms but also contributes to neuroprotection and neurological recovery.

Parkinson Disease Detection on MRI Images using Image Processing [4], Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative disorder that impairs movement and cognitive function. Early diagnosis is vital for effective treatment and disease management. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is a non-invasive diagnostic tool capable of capturing detailed images of the brain, making it useful for identifying structural changes associated with PD.

In this study, we present a method for PD detection using MRI images through a series of image processing techniques. Our approach comprises multiple stages, including preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification. The preprocessing stage involves normalization, segmentation, and registration of MRI images to eliminate noise and align them for accurate feature extraction. During feature extraction, handcrafted features such as intensity histograms, texture, and morphological attributes are used to characterize the MRI data.

For classification, we employ machine learning algorithms, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to predict PD presence based on the extracted features. We tested our approach on a publicly available dataset consisting of MRI images from both PD patients and healthy controls. The results indicate that our method achieves high levels of accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity compared to existing techniques. These results highlight the effectiveness of leveraging MRI data and deep learning models for Parkinson's Disease detection, offering a significant step towards automated and early-stage diagnosis. By utilizing advanced image processing techniques in combination with CNN-based classification, this method provides an objective and reliable tool that can aid clinicians in identifying PD and tracking its progression over time.

4. MODULES AND DESCRIPTION

4.1 Patient Recruitment

In the context of a dataset, patient recruitment has already been completed, and the dataset contains MRI scans of recruited patients. Each MRI scan is associated with metadata that includes patient characteristics like age, gender, disease stage, and diagnosis status (PD or healthy).

Fig 1.Dataset Images

4.2 MRI Scanning

The MRI scans are already present in the dataset. This step would involve ensuring the quality of the MRI scans within the dataset, verifying that they are clear, and conforming to the required standards. If new data needs to be added, MRI scanning would be conducted and appended to the existing dataset.

Fig 2. PD MRI Images.

3.3 Data Labeling

Labeling in a dataset involves categorizing each MRI scan based on known diagnosis information. Each scan would be labeled as "PD" (Parkinson's Disease) or "Control" (Healthy). Additional labels could include disease severity (e.g., mild, moderate, severe) or specific symptoms if available. Proper labeling helps train machine learning models to distinguish between PD-affected and healthy brains.

3.4 Data Preprocessing

In this step, MRI scans from the dataset are preprocessed to remove noise, standardize dimensions, and ensure consistency. Preprocessing techniques include:

- Image Registration: Aligning MRI images to a common reference frame.
- Skull Stripping: Removing non-brain elements from the image.
- Intensity Normalization: Standardizing pixel intensity values. These preprocessing steps are essential to ensure that the dataset is uniform, which improves the performance of analytical models.

5. Proposed System

Parkinson disease (PD) is a degenerative neurological disorder that cannot be treated. Rapid diagnosis can provide patients with momentary respite and decrease the course of PD.

Data collection Technique:

1. Patient Recruitment
2. MRI Scanning
3. Data Anonymization
4. Data Labeling
5. Data Preprocessing
6. Data Augmentation
7. Data Storage

Fig 4. Architecture

4.1 Upload Dataset:

The initial step involves uploading the dataset. This dataset may include various types of data such as MRI scans, clinical records, or voice samples collected from patients and healthy individuals.

4.2 Dataset Pre-processing:

In this stage, the uploaded dataset undergoes pre-processing to ensure it is in a suitable format for analysis. This step may include cleaning the data (removing noise or inconsistencies), normalization

(scaling features to a common range), or feature extraction to highlight key attributes useful for detecting Parkinson's.

4.3 Prediction of Parkinson's Disease:

Using the pre-processed dataset, machine learning models or algorithms are applied to predict whether a subject has Parkinson's Disease. This could involve analyzing patterns in MRI images, motor symptoms, or other diagnostic markers.

4.4 Detected:

If the prediction is confirmed by both the primary dataset and voice sample analysis, the disease is marked as "Detected." This decision is based on the combined results of the primary data and voice analysis.

6. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

To evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed method for Parkinson's Disease (PD) detection, we conducted a series of experiments using a publicly available MRI dataset comprising images from both PD patients and healthy controls. The experimental setup involved several key stages, including data preprocessing, feature extraction, and model training using deep learning algorithms.

6.1 Dataset Description

The dataset used in this study consisted of MRI brain images obtained from a diverse group of participants. It included both PD-affected individuals and healthy controls, ensuring a balanced representation for accurate training and testing of the model. Each MRI image underwent careful preprocessing to ensure uniformity and eliminate artifacts.

6.2 Preprocessing Techniques

During the preprocessing stage, MRI images were normalized, segmented, and registered to standardize the data. Noise reduction techniques were applied to minimize artifacts and enhance the image quality. This step was crucial in ensuring that only the relevant structural features of the brain were retained for further analysis.

6.3 Feature Extraction

The feature extraction process focused on deriving meaningful information from the preprocessed MRI images. We extracted handcrafted features, such as intensity histograms, texture descriptors, and morphological attributes, which served as inputs for the classification model. These features captured variations in brain structure that are typically associated with PD.

6.4 Model Architecture and Training

The classification was performed using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), specifically the LeNet-5 architecture, due to its effectiveness in image-based classification tasks. The network was trained using the extracted features, and the model parameters were optimized to achieve the highest

classification accuracy. To avoid overfitting, techniques like dropout and data augmentation were used during training.

6.6 Experimental Results

The experimental results demonstrated that our method achieved an overall accuracy exceeding 90% in distinguishing between PD patients and healthy controls. The model also showed high sensitivity and specificity, indicating its robustness in identifying even subtle brain changes associated with PD.

7. CONCLUSION

The early detection of Parkinson's Disease (PD) is crucial for gaining a better understanding of its causes, initiating therapeutic interventions, and developing effective treatments. This project proposed a deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model to automatically distinguish between healthy individuals and patients affected by PD.

In the future, we plan to analyze the features learned by the model more closely and adapt the PD detection method for identifying the disease at its early stages.

APPENDIX

Appendixes, if needed, appear before the acknowledgement.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The heading of this section must not be numbered. You may wish to thank those who have supported you and your work.

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